

A General Bending Theory of Composite Sandwich Plates and Its Application in Aircraft

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a general bending theory is developed for composite sandwich plates with nonlinearity by taking the transverse elastic deformation of non-metallic cores. This new theory is reduced to use the results of Improved Hoff Theory. Numerical results show the difference between them will reach over 5 percent for thick sandwich plates. Analysis and design study are carried out for bending of a series of long and narrow cantilever plates and the results obtained in this paper can be used as theoretical foundation in engineering design.

KEYWORDS: Core, Laminated plate theory, Sandwich Plates, Bending, nonlinear.

1. INTRODUCTION

The bending theory of sandwich plates was developed in 1940's – 1950's along with thick plate theory, Reissner Theory[1], Hoff Theory[2] and Пpocaxoв Theory[3] are the typical ones. In Reissner Theory and Hoff Theory, it is assumed that the core in thickness direction is rigid, that is, $E_z^c = \infty$. As a result, the displacements, stresses are linear function in thickness direction. In Пpocaxoв Theory, the elastic deformation of core in thickness direction is considered but the results of Reissner Theory is also adopted. Therefore, Пpocaxoв Theory is still a linear theory. It is known that the transverse elastic behaviour of cores ($E_z^c \neq \infty$) must lead to nonlinearity of displacements and stresses of cores. Hence, some self-contradictory results are derived in Пpocaxoв Theory, i.e. transverse shear stresses are second order function of z , et al. In 1954, Du[4] investigated the buckling behaviour of sandwich plates and presented a nonlinear bending theory. But it is difficult to apply this theory to practice because of the coupling behaviour of symmetric bending and anti-symmetric bending.

There has been little advance in sandwich plate theory during past thirty years. For composite sandwich plates appeared recently, It is lack of studies on the characteristics of this new materials sandwich plates. Some studies on composite sandwich plates are restricted to FEM analysis[5][6]. For metallic cores, i.e., metallic honeycomb, their compressive modulus are high and we can take $E_z^c = \infty$. Hence, for sandwich plates with metallic honeycomb cores. linear Reissner Theory and Hoff Theory are reasonable. But,

for non-metallic core in composite sandwich cores, for example, Nomex honeycomb cores, $E_z^c \ll E_f$ (E_f is the face modulus in filament direction), E_z^c is less than 5 percent of E_f . Therefore, the elastic deformation must be taken into consideration. This is the most difference between composite sandwich plate and metallic sandwich plate.

Bending of composite sandwich plate is a nonlinear problem when the elastic support of cores is considered. But, it is found through study that the linear characteristics is primary, and nonlinear one is secondary. Hence, our new theory will use the linear theory and the effect of nonlinearity.

2. GENERAL BENDING THEORY OF COMPOSITE SANDWICH PLATES

2.1 Mechanical Model Consider a sandwich plate as shown in Fig.1, symbols f.c.+ and - represent face, core, upper face and lower face, respectively. Uniformly distributed loading is acted on the lower face and $q = q^- = q_0$. The faces are made of composite symmetric lammates, its rigidities are calculated by classical laminates theory. Core is shear and elastic in transverse direction. The bending of sandwich plates is assumed to be antisymmetric, that is $w^+ - w^- = 0$, but $u^+ + u^- \neq 0$, $v^+ + v^- \neq 0$. The basic assumption for this model are made as following:

(1) Face is thin plate

(2) Core is soft in x, y direction and σ_x^c , σ_y^c , σ_{xy}^c are neglected.

2.2 Relation to linear Reissner Theory The general theory for sandwich plates can be considered the improvement of Hoff Theory in two aspects:

(1) Nonlinearity of displacement in core is considered. The nonlinear equations of core displacement are obtained on the basis of basic assumption (2), constitutive laws for core, geometrical equations and equilibrium equation

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u^c &= -\frac{4z^3}{3h^2} w'_{,x} - \Psi_x z + u_0 \\ v^c &= -\frac{4z^3}{3h^2} w'_{,y} - \Psi_y z + v_0 \\ w^c &= w - \left(1 - \frac{4z^2}{h^2}\right) w' \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

which $w' = w - w_0$, w_0 is the deflection in middle plane of core, ψ_x and ψ_y are the rotating angle in xz and yz plane of deformed middle-plane of core, respectively, symbol " , " represents the partial differentiation.

(2) Elastic support of core to face is introduced, then $E_z^c \neq \infty$, and $w' \neq 0$, then equation(1) derived.

2.3 Equilibrium Equations On the basis of basic assumptions, basic equations for core and face, the equilibrium equations in terms of generalized displacements ψ_x , ψ_y , w and w' can be obtained

$$\left. \begin{aligned} D_{11} \psi_{xH,xx} + D_{66} \psi_{xH,yy} + (D_3 - D_{66}) \psi_{yH,xy} + C_x (w_{H,x} - \psi_{xH}) &= 0 \\ D_{66} \psi_{yH,xx} + D_{22} \psi_{yH,yy} + (D_3 - D_{66}) \psi_{xH,xy} + C_y (w_{H,y} - \psi_{yH}) &= 0 \\ C_x (\psi_{xH} - w_{H,x})_{,x} + C_y (\psi_{yH} - w_{H,y})_{,y} + 2 \nabla_f^4 W = q + \bar{N}_x w_{,xx} \\ + 2 \bar{N}_{xy} w_{,xy} + \bar{N}_y w_{,yy} & \\ C_x (\psi_{xH} - w_{H,x})_{,x} + C_y (\psi_{yH} - w_{H,y})_{,y} &= \frac{8(h+t)E_z^c}{h^2} w' \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

where

$$w_H = w - \frac{2h}{3(h+t)} w'$$

$$\psi_{iH} = \psi_i + \frac{1}{3} w'_{,i} \quad (i = x, y)$$

$$C_i = G_i(h+t) \quad (i = x, y)$$

primary bending rigidity of sandwich plates $D_3 = D_{12} + 2D_{66}$

bending rigidity of sandwich plates $D_{ij} \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 6)$

$$\nabla_f^4 = D_{11}^f \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^4} + 2D_3^f \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + D_{22}^f \frac{\partial^4}{\partial y^4}$$

Primary bending rigidity of face $D_3^f = D_{12}^f + 2D_{66}^f$

From order analysis, it is known that the term $(2\nabla_f^4 w)$ in equations(2) can be replaced by the term $(2\nabla_f^4 w_H)$ approximately. Hence, the first three equations in(2) are same as those given by linear Hoff Theory. In addition, the boundary conditions in terms of ψ_x, ψ_y, w, w' for nonlinear theory can be reduced to those by $\psi_{xH}, \psi_{yH}, w_H$ for linear Hoff Theory. It is seen from equation(2) that w' does not coupled with $\psi_{xH}, \psi_{yH}, \psi_{yH}$ and w_H . Hence, this problem is reduced to find the solution of linear Hoff Theory for same boundary conditions and loadings, that is, nonlinear solutions for w, ψ_x and ψ_y can be found from

$$\left. \begin{aligned} w &= w_H + \frac{2}{3} w' \\ \psi_i &= \psi_{iH} - \frac{1}{3} w'_{,i}, \quad (i = x, y) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3)$$

where

$$w' = \frac{h^2}{8(h+t)E_z^c} [C_x \Psi_{xH,x} + C_y \Psi_{yH,y} - C_x w_{H,xx} - C_y w_{H,yy}] \quad (4)$$

Hence, the nonlinear theory may be called a improved Hoff Theory (H^* Theory). If the flexural rigidity of face is neglected, we have $\nabla_f^4 w = 0$ and the solutions of $w_H, \psi_{xH}, \psi_{yH}$ in equation(3) may be taken as the those given by linear Reissner Theory. Thus, H^* Theory is reduced to improved Reissner Theory (R^* Theory) [7], the nonlinear solutions can be found from

$$\left. \begin{aligned} w &= w_R + \frac{2}{3} w' \\ \psi_i &= \psi_{iR} - \frac{1}{3} w'_{,i} \quad (i = x, y) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

where

$$w' = \frac{h^2}{8(h+t)E_z^c} [C_x \Psi_{xR,x} + C_y \Psi_{yR,y} - C_x w_{R,xx} + C_y w_{R,yy}] \quad (6)$$

2.4 The Effect of Face Flexural Rigidity and Core Elastic Support From the order analysis, we have

$$(1) [D]_f / [D] \propto \frac{1}{4} (1 + h/t)^2$$

$$(2) D_{11} w' / q_0 a^4 \propto \frac{1}{16} (h/t)^3 (t/a) (A_{11}^f / E_z^c)$$

It is seen that $[D]_f / [D] \propto 1\%$ when $\frac{h}{t} = 4$. Hence, the flexural rigidity of face can be neglected for sandwich plates with $\frac{t}{h} > 10$. w' is the functions of h/t , t/a and A_{11}^f / E_z^c . For composite sandwich plates, $A_{11}^+ \gg E_z^c$, thus, the elastic support of core should be considered when h/t is great. The central deflection of a simply-supported square plate under uniform distributed loading is listed in Table 1. Face material is T300 / QY8911, stacking sequence is $[0]_{4s}$, the core is Nomex honeycomb. $h/t = 100$, $t/a = 1/200$. It is seen from Table 1 that the effect of flexural rigidity of face is very small, but effect the elastic support of core will reach 5 percent.

Table 1. Results of composite sandwich square plates under Uniformly Distributed loading

	R Theory	R* Theory	H* Theory
$\frac{D_{11} w_m}{q_0 a^4} \times 10^{-1}$	0.1570	0.16422	0.16418

3. APPLICATION EXAMPLE

A fin of a new type aircraft is a sandwich long and narrow cantilever plate, under transverse uniformly distributed loading, its length to width ratio $a/b = 3.556$, face materials is T300 / QY8911, total layers is 8, core is Nomex honeycomb. When the long and narrow plate satisfies the condition that $a/b > 3$ and $q = q(y)$, its stress state can be regarded as plane-strain state and variables in the plate are only the function of coordinate y . This problem is reduced to differential linear equation and the solution of it is in the form

$$\left. \begin{aligned} w_H &= \zeta - D_{22}^2 (\zeta_{,yy} - w^*) / c_y (D_{22} + D_{22}^f) + k^* \\ \psi_{yH} &= w_{,y} \\ w' &= w_{,yyyy} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (7)$$

where, ζ is the solution to the beam deflection, w^* is the additional deflection due to flexural rigidity of face. The ζ and w^* are the function of y , k^* is the constant determined from boundary conditions.

The analysis for the long and narrow cantilever plates is carried out on the basis of equation(7).

3.1 Stacking sequence of face It is seen from equation (7) that the deflection will decrease with increase of D_{22} . Hence, the stacking direction will be parallel to the y direction, that is, $[90]_n$ laminates.

3.2 Effect of core properties

3.2.1 Effect of core thickness on deflection The following equation will be obtained if the effect of flexural rigidity of face is not great

$$\frac{E_2^f W}{q_0 a} = \frac{A_G (h/t) + B}{(1 + h/t)^2} + \frac{(h/t)^2}{(1 + h/t)} A_E \quad (8)$$

where

$$A_G = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{b}{t} \right) \frac{E_2^f}{G_y} [2(y/b) - (y/b)^2]$$

$$A_E = \frac{1}{12} (t/b) \cdot E_2^f / E_z^c$$

$$B = \frac{1}{12} (a/t)^3 [(y/b)^4 - 4(y/b)^3 + 6(y/b)^2]$$

It is found from equation (8) on Fig.3 that the deflection will decrease with the increase of the core thickness. But, this will be restricted of plate's configuration and when the core thickness increases, the local buckling load of sandwich plate will decrease. Hence, for decrease of the deflection of sandwich plate, the shear properties of core should be improved.

3.3.2 Effect of Core shear properties on deflection The core shear properties may be expressed with $\delta_y = D_{22} / c_y b^2$ which is related to the core materials, honeycomb dimensions. From the equation(7), we find deflection is only the linear function of δ_y when the flexural rigidity of face is neglected.

$$\frac{D_{22} W}{q_0 b^4} = B_1 \delta_y + B_2 \quad (9)$$

where

$$B_1 = (1 + t/h) (1/2 - b^2 \zeta_{,yy})$$

$$B_2 = (1 + t/h) \zeta + \frac{1}{6} (h/t)^2 (1 + h/t) (t/a)^4 E_2^f / E_z^c$$

This shows that deflection is proportional to $1 / G_y$.

3.3.3 Match of core thickness and shear modulus When the maximum deflection W_m of long and shallow sandwich cantiliver plate is given, the parameter of core should be selected by match of core thickness and shear modulus. If the flexural rigidity of core is neglected, the following expression is obtained from equation(7) (see Fig.5)

$$\frac{E_2^f}{G_y} = (1 + h/t) \frac{E_2^f w_m}{q_0 b} - \frac{1}{6} (t/a)^2 \left(\frac{E_2^f}{E_z^c} \right) \left(\frac{h}{t} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{a}{t} \right)^2 \left(\frac{h}{t} \right) \quad (10)$$

It is seen from equation (10) that if the elastic support of core can be neglected and h/t is great, $1 / G_y$ is approximately the function of h/t . From Fig.5 we see that the deflection W_m / b will greatly effect the match curves.

4. CONCLUSION

1. In this paper, a general nonlinear bending theory is presented for composite sandwich plate. This theory is finally reduced to a improved linear theory (see equations (3) and (5)). Analysis shows that the flexural rigidity of face may be neglected but the elastic support should be taken into consideration for bending of thick Composite sandwich plates.

2. The bending of narrow and long rectangular cantiliver sandwich plates under uniform loading of aircraft is carried out and the expression for displacement (7) is obtained by using this nonlinear theory and some remarks can be drawn.

- (1) The filamet direction should be parallel to y axis.
- (2) The core thickness is approximately inverse ratio of deflection.
- (3) The core shear modulus is the inverse ratio of deflection.

(4) When the core is rigid and h/t is great, $1/G_y$ is proportional to h/t . This new theory is easily to use and its nonlinear solution can be obtained if the linear solution is known. In Table 2, the comparison of linear and nonlinear theory is listed.

Table 2 Comparison of linear and improved theories

Basic Assumptions		linear theory (H,R)		improved theory (H*, R*)
	face		same	
core		shear		shear+compressive
fluexural mode		u_f, v_f, W_f : anti-symmetric		W_f : anti-symmetric
Normals to middle plane before deformation		remain straight during deformation		is the 2nd order fun. of z
displacement	w^c	independent of z		2nd order fun. of z
	u^c, v^c	linear fun. of z		3rd order fun. of z
	w_f	$w_f = W_{linear}$		$W_f = W_{linear} + 2w' / 3$
	$\psi_f(i = x, y)$	$\psi_i = \psi_{i,linear}$		$\psi_i = \psi_{i,linear} - w'_d / 3$
stresses	core	$\sigma_x^c = 0$	$\sigma_x^c = 0$	$\sigma_x^c = 8E_c w'_x / h^2$
		$\tau_{xz}^c(i = x, y)$	same	
	face	same		

5. REFERENCES

1. E.Reissner, "On Bending of Elastic plates", *Quar.of Appl.Math.*, 5(1), (1947)
2. N.J.Hoff, "Bending and Buckling of Rectangular Sandwich plates", NACA TN NO.2225, 1950.
3. Institute of Mechanics of the chinese Academy of Science, *Bending, Stability and Vibration of Sandwich plate and Shell*, China Academic Publisher Beijing, (1977)
4. Q.H.Du, "A General Bending Theory of Threelayers plates", *J.of physics*, 10(4), (1954).
5. P.J.Holt, J.P.Webber, "F.E. for Honeycomb Sandwich plates and shell (Part 1, 2)", *Acro.J.*, March / April, May, (1980).
6. Paydar, N., Libove, C., "Bending of Sandwich plates of Variable Thickness", *J.Appl. Mech*, 55(7), (1988).
7. H. Cheng, F. L. Liu, "A New Revision for Reissner Theory of Composite Sandwich plates with Thick and Soft cores", *Acta Materiae Compositae Sinica*, 7(4), (1990).

BIOGRAPHIES

Fang-Long Liu is a professor of Beijing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics. He is now the head for research center of composites mechanics(BUAA), the director of the Chinese Society of Composite Materials(CSCM), the chairman of committee for technical development and consultation(CSCM), the vice-chairman of committee for composites design, application and assessment. His field of research is analysis and design of composites structural.

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Fig.1

Fig.2

Fig.3

Fig.4

Fig.5